

PARENTAL MIGRATION: ITS EFFECT TO STUDENTS' BEHAVIOR AND COGNITIVE SKILLS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 4

Pages: 509-516

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2074

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12789146

Manuscript Accepted: 08-30-2023

Parental Migration: Its Effect to Students' Behavior and Cognitive Skills

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study is to determine the effect of parental migration on students' behavior and cognitive skills. This study sought to answer the following questions: (1) How do the respondents describe the migration of parents abroad in terms of education, work, and Income? (2) What is the perception of the respondents on students' behavior? (3) How do the respondents perceive students' cognitive skills? (4) Does Parental Migration significantly affect behavior and cognitive skills of the students? A survey questionnaire was used in collecting data and information. The survey was conducted on a face-to-face modality in St. Mary's Academy of Nagcarlan during the class in Araling Panlipunan. The descriptive correlational study method was used in order to gather data together with related sources of information for an accurate interpretation of findings. The main data obtained were treated statistically with the use of the percentage and frequency distribution, weighted mean, standard deviation and Pearson for inferential questions with a .05 level of significance to determine if there is a significant effect. The test of significance within the variables reveals that there are variables that do not have a significant effect on students' behavior and cognitive skills, thus, partially accepting the null hypothesis.

Keywords: *migration, behavior, cognitive skills*

Introduction

Individuals relocate to enhance their lives and the lives of their families, acquire new skills and experiences, find employment, or escape insecurity or famine. Many people around the world seek better lives outside their own country. In a study by Dimurger 2013, *Migration and Families Left Behind*, remittances are regarded as an economic benefit of labor migration to the family members left behind. The Philippines is one of Asia's nations, providing labor resources to neighboring countries. In exchange, it is the growing percentage of remittances sent by our OFW and more plight of children being left behind.

Migration is an economic, social, and political process that affects those who migrate, those who remain, and the destinations they settle in. Moreover, the advent of globalization has made labor migration a global phenomenon. People cross borders for improved employment opportunities and a brighter future for their families. Along with this trend, more children are being abandoned by one or both parents, leaving them in the care of extended family members—and household helpers.

Parents leave the country to seek a good salary that will support their children with financial and educational resources to perform well in school. They want to uplift their economic status by working abroad, earning considerable money. Ming Chen Fu et al. (2017) pointed out in their study; *Parental Absence Accompanies Worse Academic Achievements*, that parents' engagement in children's school or home activities was associated with higher academic achievement. Being separated from their parents can severely affect children's academic achievement and their behavior toward life situations. The number of years the parents stay abroad can lessen the bond between parents and children, leading to the consciousness of being abandoned. This creates a gap that can never be replaced by material things that can be bought with their remittances. The majority of children left behind were impacted. This kind of consciousness leads them to rebellion to catch their parents' attention. Usually, the target of their rebellion is their studies. It will start with cutting classes, untoward behavior, and absences, affecting their school performance. The danger of taking illegal drugs, early pregnancy, and teenage marriage is much more with that kind of rebellious activity.

Many parents choose to work abroad without them knowing that it can affect their children's behavior and academic performance at school. They believed that having enough resources for their children's educational needs would make them achieve their schooling. Another is a stable position that generates a substantial income to support their children. This study aims to determine the effect of Parental Migration on students' academic behavior and cognitive abilities. This study seeks to determine whether Parental Migration has significantly affected students' academic behavior and cognitive skills.

Research Questions

This study aimed to ascertain the impact of parental migration on the academic behavior and cognitive abilities of students. This study sought to answer the following specific questions:

1. How do respondents view the overseas migration of parents in terms of :
 - 1.1. education;
 - 1.2. work; and
 - 1.3. income?
2. What is the perception of the respondents on students' behavior?
3. How do the respondents perceive students' cognitive skills?

4. Does Parental Migration significantly affect the students' behavior and cognitive skills?

Literature Review

The history of Migration Santos (2014) started in the 1970s when Filipino men left the Philippines to work in the Middle East construction site and oil rigs. They were considered OCW – Overseas Contract Workers. "Katas ng Saudi" is a famous phrase that refers to the material benefits and results of working in Saudi Arabia to gain a better life. Filipino women began leaving the country to fill domestic and caregiving vacancies in developed countries and Asia during the '80s and '90s. Today Filipino dominated fields of seafaring, domestic work, and nursing have become the way of life of many Filipino families and made our country a significant source of labor migrants for many nations worldwide.

In Asia, the Philippines has witnessed the largest outflow of permanent emigrants and migrant labor over the past three to four decades, according to Tan (2018). The number of people living and working abroad has reached nearly 8% of the population, and the annual outflow of employees to increasingly diverse destinations and occupations is approximately 14% of the labor force.

According to an article published by the Scalabrini Migration Center in 2017, Migration can influence the education and skills sector of a country of origin, such as the Philippines, in multiple ways. Due to the absence of familial guidance and support, the education and academic performance of the children of emigrants may be negatively affected. When both parents migrate, it is also possible for older children to be forced to assume the caregiving and other domestic responsibilities of adult family members, which could force them to opt out of school.

Having OFW parents, the father or mother, who work abroad to generate a high income and support their children's requirements, particularly in education. Education is essential for progress and development. One of the most critical responsibilities of a parent today is to take the millennial generation of students seriously. Because sending their children to a formal school is difficult, it is also challenging to keep an eye on them and provide them with the appropriate encouragement.

According to Maculada's (2017) study, The Effect of Having an OFW Parent on a Student's Academic Performance, family structure, household resources, number of siblings competing for those resources, and parent's educational attainment are frequently significant predictors of children's education outcomes.

According to Maculada's (2017) research, the export of labor has been an official policy for decades, requiring many parents to abandon their children. Overseas Migration of Filipino parents has increased the number of long-term separations between parents and their offspring.

According to Lobos et al. (2019), overseas labor has become a viable solution for one in twelve Filipino families' problems. It has resulted in unavoidable consequences for children left behind, despite providing opportunities for a better and more financially secure life. The rising number of Filipino migrant laborers poses challenges for families in providing for their children's needs and ensuring that they receive the necessary support despite geographical distances. The lack of emotional support for their children, which harms their well-being, is a significant problem for OFW families due to parental absence.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, a descriptive correlational research design was used to determine the relationship between parental migration and students' cognitive and behavioral skills. According to McBurney and White (2009), descriptive correlational design is utilized in research studies that provide static depictions of situations and determine the relationship between variables.

Participants

Involve a total of forty-nine (49) participants. The respondents are grade seven (7) and grade eight (8) students whose parents are working abroad. This was conducted at St. Mary's Academy of Nagcarlan.

Instruments

A survey interview questionnaire was used by the researcher in collecting data. The survey was done on a face-to-face modality. The questionnaire was used to assess the impact of parental migration on the students' behavior and cognitive skills. The survey interview questionnaire has 4 parts. Part 1 is the demographic profile which are the name (optional), age, grade level, gender, parent in abroad and workplace. Part 2 contains the indicators of socio-economic status namely education, work, and income and an interview question. Part 3 was the indicators for students' behavior and students' cognitive skills.

Procedure

The researcher prepared a letter of request to the College Dean and to the researcher's adviser for the conduct of the study. A letter of consent prepared by the researcher was given to the School Principal in order to request for a formal approval on the participation of the respondents. The letter also included statements on data privacy, assuring that only the researcher will be exposed to all information

that will be given all throughout the survey. As the request was approved, the researcher conducted the study. The survey interview questionnaire was distributed to the respondents during their Araling Panlipunan class. After the collection of data, qualitative and quantitative treatment was applied in order to determine the result of the study.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher consider the Privacy of data of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section contains various tables that present the data of this study's findings and their respective statistical data treatment-derived interpretations.

The tables contain information about respondents' perceptions of parental Migration's impact on students' behavior and cognitive abilities.

Table 1. *Education-Related Implications of Parental Migration*

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I experience educational difficulties especially in dealing with my activities because of my parent/s' migration	2.61	1.04	Moderately Agree
2. I do not have the motivation to continue my studies due to a lack of guidance from my parent/s who migrated.	2.02	1.13	Disagree
3. I cannot focus on my studies because of my parent/s' migration to work abroad.	1.98	0.92	Disagree
4. I am reluctant and lousy because no one guides me in my studies.	1.92	0.98	Disagree
5. I feel abandoned and neglected during school activities that need the presence of parents.	2.10	1.37	Disagree
6. I am inspired because my parents work hard for my studies.	4.45	1.00	Strongly Agree
7. I am happy because I have all my resources to continue my studies.	4.65	0.52	Strongly Agree
8. I am grateful to my parents for planning my studies.	4.61	0.79	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.04	0.44	Moderately Highly Effective

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Not Effective 1.50- 2.49 Less Effective 2.50- 3.49 Moderately Highly Effective 3.50-4.49 Highly Effective 4.50-5.00- Very High Effective

The seventh statement, "I am happy because I have all the resources I need to continue my studies," received the highest mean score of 4.65 with a standard deviation of 0.52 and was interpreted as Strongly Agree by the respondents. This situation shows that the respondents are free from thinking about how to meet their needs for school expenses. In this case, the respondents can focus directly on their studies. In contrast, the fourth statement, "I am hesitant and poor in my studies because no one guides me," received a mean of 1.92 and a standard deviation of 0.98, interpreted as Disagree. Showed that the respondents disagreed with the statement because some members of the family helped and guided them, particularly their grandparents. In some instances, good communication with their parents abroad became a tool to guide the left-behind children, like frequent video calls, private messages using Facebook or Messenger, and even electronic emails to communicate about the status of their studies and life activities while the parents are away.

The aggregate mean of 3.04 and standard deviation of 0.44, verbally interpreted as Moderately Highly Effective in terms of Education, indicates that one way or another, the Migration of parents abroad affects the respondent's Education. It may imply that the respondents, although they sometimes have difficulty dealing with their school activities, are still motivated, inspired, and can focus on their studies. They are also thankful, and they do not think that they are being neglected or abandoned because their parents work hard to give their best in providing for their educational needs. The result is supported by the research of Xinxin Chen et al. (2009), which indicates that the educational performance of migrant households improves. The reality that parental Migration is of great help as a source of financial support to the left behind children and their families makes the respondents gain access to their Education.

However, it contradicts the findings of Maculada (2017), which suggest that parental absence may predict adverse educational outcomes for children. The caregiving arrangement is essential in every migrant household because the absence of the primary caregiver can affect the respondents' focus on their studies

The table 2 shows that statement eight, "My parents' work motivates me to do my best in my study," averaged 4.41 with a standard deviation of 0.89, verbally interpreted as Agree. The respondents Agree with the statement because they know that their parents opt to work far away to sustain their needs, most importantly, their educational needs. Moreover, this inspired them to do their task and activities in school. The verbal interpretation of a mean of 1.88 and a standard deviation of 1.03 disagrees with the second statement, "I do not have the eagerness to study because my parents need to leave me to work far away." The respondents Disagree with the statement because the respondents' appreciation of the kind of Work of their parents made them enthusiastic about their studies. Their awareness or orientation on the Work their parents have made the respondents believe they should give their best in studying as a reward for their parents.

Table 2. *Effect of Parental Migration on Work*

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I experience educational difficulties especially in dealing with my activities because of my parent/s work as OFW migrant worker	2.24	1.07	Disagree
2. I do not have the eagerness to study because my parents need to leave me to work far away.	1.88	1.03	Disagree
3. I feel insecure and out of place with others because my parents are not around to guide me due to the distance of their work.	2.29	1.27	Disagree
4. I am noisy inside the classroom because I want to seek attention to feel that I am cared for since my parents are at their job and cannot attend to me.	2.24	1.32	Disagree
5. I come to school on time even if my parents work a distance of miles away leaving me with the care of my guardian.	3.63	1.32	Agree
6. I attend my classes regularly and participate actively in discussions and activities to earn good grades as a way of gratefulness to my parents work abroad	4.22	0.82	Agree
7. I can focus on my studies with the guidance of my guardian because my parents work abroad.	4.31	0.98	Agree
8. My parent's work gives me the motivation to do my best in my study	4.41	0.89	Agree
Overall	3.15	0.39	Moderately Highly Effective

Legend: 1.00 -1.49 Not Effective 1.50- 2.49 Less Effective 2.50- 3.49 Moderately Highly Effective 3.50-4.49 Highly Effective 4.50-5.00- Very High Effective

The overall mean of 3.15, standard deviation of 0.39, and verbally interpreted as Moderately Highly Effective. The result indicates that respondents have a favorable view of the type of Work performed by their parents abroad, which motivates them, to focus on their studies, attend classes regularly, come to school on time, are not noisy inside the classroom, and can interact socially with others. This also happens because of their guardian's help in accomplishing the tasks and activities in school.

It is supported by the study of Dimurger 2017, stating that the effect of a family member's Migration to work abroad, based on particular circumstances, the impact on those left behind can be either positive or negative. Based on this, Parental Migration positively affects the respondents' perception of the kind of work their parents do.

Most of the time, the left-behind children learn the concept of work appreciating the kind of Work of their parents. Furthermore, it includes the fact that they will separate for a while from each other due to the kind of Work their parents have. It leads them to be grateful and value the hardships of their parents in order for them to continue their studies and achieve their goals.

Table 3. *Effect of Parental Migration to Income*

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I feel happy because my parent's income can provide for our needs.	4.59	0.67	Strongly Agree
2. I am extravagant because my parent's income is too much for my needs.	2.65	1.27	Moderately Agree
3. The income of my parents makes me feel secure even if I will not finish my studies.	2.94	1.42	Moderately Agree
4. I can buy what I want from the salary of my parents	2.69	1.19	Moderately Agree
5. I learn to budget my daily allowance	4.10	1.05	Agree
6. I always treat my friends and classmates	3.00	1.22	Moderately Agree
7. I only buy essential things needed for my study	4.06	0.90	Agree
8. I learned to be generous because I have all what I need	3.98	0.95	Agree
Overall	3.50	0.58	Highly Effective

Legend: 1.00 -1.49 Not Effective 1.50- 2.49 Less Effective 2.50- 3.49 Moderately Highly Effective 3.50-4.49 Highly Effective 4.50-5.00

Overseas Workers work abroad to gain enough money to support their families, especially the Education of their children. Statement number one, "I feel happy because my parent's income can provide for our needs," A score of 4.59 with a standard deviation of 0.67, was interpreted orally as Strong Agreement. It indicates that the respondents are satisfied with their parents' Income because it meets their needs. It may make the respondents feel good knowing that their parents' Income can provide for primary and educational needs. They will no longer worry about where to get money for their expenses at home and in school.

While statement number two, "I am extravagant because my parent's Income is too much for my need, possesses a mean of 2.65 and a standard deviation of 1.27, which can be interpreted as Moderately Agree. The respondents agree with the statement because the parents or guardians who are left with them allow them to spend money on the things they want aside from their basic needs, like gadgets and accessories.

The aggregate mean Income of 3.50 and standard deviation of 0.58 is interpreted orally as Highly Effective. It means their parents' Income while working abroad makes them feel secure and confident that they can buy their needs. Parental Migration also taught the respondents to budget their allowance, even if they always treat classmates and friends. Hence they also learned the concept of buying the essential things needed in school, and most importantly, they learned to become generous to others. They learned to lend things and

sometimes give some things that their friends or classmates needed to meet the requirements in school.

The result is supported by the article Why Filipinos Work Abroad (2021), which states that OFW parents' top reason for working abroad is to gain higher salaries and benefits to support their families being left behind. Families who receive funds from relatives abroad are provided with greater purchasing power. Income gave the left-behind children and their families the confidence to buy their basic needs and wants.

Furthermore, Avila (2012) stated that when the family becomes stable, it can withstand the separation caused by Migration, and the children of migrants perceive that their family is doing well. This may be the reason why sometimes the left-behind children become extravagant.

Students Behavior

Table 4. *Effect of Parental Migration on Students' Behavior*

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I always tells the truth	3.53	0.79	Agree
2. I respect others and sacred places.	4.35	0.78	Agree
3. I recite and lead prayer in class with proper decorum	3.88	0.78	Agree
4. Shows refinement in speech and actions.	3.96	0.82	Agree
5. Abides by the rules of the school, community, and country.	4.31	0.80	Agree
6. Respect the flag and national anthem.	4.59	0.61	Strongly Agree
7. Takes care of school materials, facilities and equipment.	4.33	0.75	Agree
8. Punctual in class and prompt in meeting responsibilities and other required projects and activities.	3.71	0.98	Agree
Overall	4.08	0.55	Observable

Legend: 1.00 -1.49 Not Observable 1.50- 2.49 Less Observable 2.50- 3.49 Moderately Observable 3.50-4.49 Observable 4.50-5.00- Highly Observable

The table presents the behavior of the respondents in each given statement. Statement number 6, "Respect the flag and national anthem," Strongly Agree, was verbally interpreted from the highest mean of 4.59 and standard deviation of 0.61. This indicates that the respondents revere the country's national symbols as instructed in school. While statement number one, "I always tell the truth," The data, which has a mean of 3.53 and a standard deviation of 0.79, is interpreted orally as Agree. The respondents Agree to the statement simply because they know what will be the consequence if they tell a lie. They might fear how their parents or guardians will treat or react to them when they do not tell the truth.

The mean of 4.08 and the standard deviation of 0.55 are interpreted verbally as observable. The respondents show appropriate observable behavior in school by respecting and caring for the school's properties, following rules and regulations, and coming to school on time to attend their classes. Proper behavior is also observed in a community member by respecting others and sacred places and communicating with others by using appropriate words and refinement in their actions.

As a student of a Catholic School, the respondents observe proper decorum in reciting and leading prayers in class. A noticeable proper behavior is observed, even though the respondents were left by their parents while working abroad. The result is contrary to the study of Yana (2014), stating that the left-behind children's academic and social-psychological development will be negatively affected due to a lack of companionship and discipline from parents.

According to Burgos et al., 2020, even though the purpose of Migration is financial stability, the family composition change can adversely affect the children left behind. The sudden change in family composition caused by a parent's absence may impact the well-being and upbringing of the children. Since almost all the respondents were left in the care of their mother, they were guided to be a person of good character. Mother is the prime caregiver and good influencer. Their mothers' guidance and support made them feel secure and loved, making the respondents' perspectives positive toward life situations.

Students' Cognitive Skills

Parents somehow expect excellent grades from their children in their school performances. The table shows how parental Migration affects the respondents' cognitive skills. Statement number one, "I can stay focused on a single task for a long time even if parents are not around," the mean is 4.12, and the standard deviation is 0.92, verbally interpreted as Agree. This means that the respondents, even if their parents work abroad, can concentrate on the tasks given to them. The awareness of their financial stability may be one factor in that situation because they do not need to think about where they will get the resources they need for their studies.

Statement number three possesses a mean of 2.10 and a standard deviation of 1.05. "I cannot understand the lesson discussed because I feel neglected and abandoned by my parents" is verbally interpreted as Disagree. The respondents Disagree with the statement simply because they have some family members who take good care of them and guide and help them in their school activities. The care and guidance of their guardian helped the respondents not to have a feeling of being abandoned and neglected.

The mean is 3.24, and the standard deviation is 0.44. is verbally interpreted as Moderately Evident. This indicates that the cognitive skills of the respondents are slightly affected by parental Migration. The result is supported by the findings of Navarez et al. (2017),

who state that children need tangible support as they face a variety of challenges that extend beyond the cognitive domain, elaborating that children who are separated from their parents as a result of Migration are more likely to experience a decline in classroom performance. This is because the respondents, based on the statements it is interpreted as moderately agree, reveal that Even though they were left with the guidance of their relatives, they still yearn for the love, care, and guidance of their biological parents

Table 5. *Effect of Parental Migration on Students' Cognitive Skills*

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I can stay focused on a single task for long periods of time even if my parents are not around.	4.12	0.90	Agree
2. I can focus on one single task despite other distractions around me.	3.57	1.04	Agree
3. I cannot understand the lesson discussed because I feel neglected and abandoned by my parents.	2.10	1.05	Disagree
4. I am always confused with the lessons and activities because my guardian cannot help me to do it.	2.53	1.16	Moderately Agree
5. I can retain a series of instructions without having to stop and look back at the tasks repeatedly.	3.20	1.19	Moderately Agree
6. I cannot comply to submit on time my tasks and activities in class because I have no idea how to do it..	2.51	1.12	Moderately Agree
7. I understand the lesson well.	3.96	0.98	Agree
8. I can do my assignments without the help of my guardian	3.96	0.93	Agree
Overall	3.24	0.44	Moderately Evident

Legend: 1.00 -1.49 Not Evident 1.50- 2.49 Less Evident 2.50- 3.49 Moderately Evident 3.50-4.49 Evident 4.50-5.00- Highly Evident

Table no. 6 shows that education as an effect of parental Migration has a significant effect on Students' Behavior, having a value of -.346, which is significant at the 0.01 level. However, regarding Students' Cognitive skills and education, there is no significant relationship with the value of .121. In this kind of result, the null hypothesis is partially rejected. The result indicates that the Migration of parents has something to do with the attitude of the respondents toward their studies. The respondents are motivated to study well, even if their parents leave them.

Table 6. *Effect of Parental Migration on Students' Behavior and Cognitive Skills*

Effect of Parental Migration in Terms of	Student's Behavior	Student's Cognitive skills
Education	-.346*	.121
Work	-.169	.248
Income	.492**	.524**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

This result is supported by the findings of Xu and Xie (2015) and Zhou et al. (2015), who state that no significant impact of parental Migration on children's Education, specifically academic performance, has been discovered by other researchers. As the potential adverse effects of parental Migration may be mitigated by other forms of support, such as elders, parental Migration may have a net positive influence on children. Moreover, most of the respondents are left with the guidance of their mothers.

Furthermore, it was revealed that Students' Behavior with the value of -.169 and Students' Cognitive skills with the value of .248 have no significant effect on their parents' Work abroad. The null hypothesis is therefore adopted. It indicates that parental Migration in terms of employment has no significant effect on students' behavior and cognitive skills. The factors are not revealed in this study. The guardian manages the respondents' behavior well, which is why the result is contrary to the study of Zhao 2017, stating that evidence has indicated that parental migrations affect child well-being through a trade-off between increased family income and disrupted parental care. In addition, the result contradicts the findings of Burgos et al. (2020) in that, while the motivation for parental Migration is financial stability, the absence of a parent may impact the children's well-being and upbringing. Thus, the respondents' awareness about their financial status because of the Work their parents have helped them appreciate their parents' purpose in working abroad, which is why they were inspired and eager to study well and behave appropriately.

Regarding Income as an Effect of Parental Migration, the results showed a significant effect between Income and the Students' Behavior, with a value of .492, and with the Students' Cognitive Skills, with a value of .524. The values are significant at the 0.05 level, and the null hypothesis is disproved with these data. It implies that parental Migration affects the students' behavior, particularly the essence of managing financial resources.

According to the research of Botezat (2014), Migration may have positive or negative effects on the children left behind. When the respondents know that they have many resources, they tend to feel secure, making them motivated and focused on their tasks in school. Family stability, particularly financial stability, made the respondents confident about the budget needed for their studies and have the confidence to treat friends and classmates because they have the resources to spend.

It is inferred that some variables do not have a significant effect, such as education on students' cognitive skills and occupation on

students' behavior and cognitive skills. This is contrary to the study of Ming Chen Fu et al. (2017), stating that being separated from their parent can significantly affect academic achievement and behavior in response to life situations. The result reveals that parental Migration has no effect on the respondents' behavior and cognitive skills may be because of the kind of guidance given to them by their guardians. The behavior and cognitive skills of the respondents remain fine even if their parents work abroad.

Conclusions

Based on this study's findings, the following conclusions are drawn: It was found that there are variables that do not have a significant effect on students' behavior and cognitive skills, thus, partially accepting the null hypothesis.

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